

THE EFFECTS OF FIBER CONTENT AND CHEMICAL TREATMENTS ON THE MECHANICAL AND MORPHOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF POLYESTER BLEND BIODEGRADABLE COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: An attempt was made at increasing both toughness and rigidity by simultaneous toughening and reinforcement. Natural fiber-reinforced biodegradable polyester blend composites were prepared from modified /unmodified biodegradable polyesters blends with surface treated and untreated jute fibers by melt mixing and subsequent molding. The resulting crosslinked and uncrosslinked Poly (lactic acid)/poly (caprolactone) blends were used as the biodegradable polyester matrixes. Alkali treatment was performed as the surface treatments on the jute fiber. The tensile and flexural moduli of all the fiber-reinforced composites increased with fiber content. The effect of surface treatment on the morphology and subsequent mechanical properties was also studied. The blending of PLA with PCL alleviated the brittleness of PLA. Moreover, a remarkable increase in the ductility of the blend was obtained due to crosslinking while the addition of surface modified jute simultaneously improved stiffness and strength.

KEYWORDS; Polylactic acid/polycaprolactone blend, alkali-treated jute, biocomposites, dicumyl peroxide, crosslinking, mechanical properties

INTRODUCTION

Further advances in science and technology in a world that has witnessed the most of its technological advancement within the last 60 years is leading to more affluence and increased demand on limited non-renewable resources. Hence the current emphasis is to develop materials that are renewable and sustainable as alternatives to the fixed petroleum or mineral based ones. There is also the need for degradability or recyclability hence the use of biodegradable polymers and natural fibers in composites. Since the last decade of the past century tremendous developments have been taking place in the pursuance of “green

biomaterials” [1-3]. Biodegradable polymers have been enjoying wide applications in the medical and pharmaceutical fields where cost is not so much of a deterrent. However biodegradable plastics are yet to make a meaningful impact in the commodity plastics industry mainly due to high cost, limitation due to production logistics or the inherently weak resistance of the biodegradable plastics and natural fibers to the environment.

Fortunately tremendous advances are being made in the development of biodegradable plastics that are affordable with the requisite mechanical properties so that they can compete in both respects with the reigning materials. [2] Poly lactic acid being a biodegradable plastic with corn as the starting raw material is envisaged to attain commodity status. One of the main limitations of PLA however, is its brittleness so several studies have been focused on this issue. However, cost reduction via the incorporation of cheap fillers that are equally biodegradable should be an equally strong objective.

The use of natural fibers as fillers in polymeric matrices is becoming more popular because they offer high specific stiffness and strength, processing flexibility with minimal harm to equipment and personnel. They are renewable, with low cost and amenable to chemical modification. Natural fibers like jute and hemp etc. can be incorporated in polymers including those based on biodegradable polymer matrixes to achieve the specified properties in the resulting biocomposites. However, high level of moisture absorption, poor wettability and insufficient adhesion between untreated fiber and the polymer matrix lead to debonding with age. In order to improve the above qualities, various surface treatments are carried out which results in improved mechanical performance of the composites. Among all modifications, alkali treatment and acetylating have been found to yield outstanding results [2].

The number of studies that have been reported on PLA biocomposites is rather limited because most investigations on PLA are focused on the improvement of its brittleness as conventional fiber reinforcement result in decrease in toughness. Here, an attempt was made at increasing toughness and rigidity by simultaneous toughening and reinforcement. Natural fiber-reinforced biodegradable polyester blend composites were prepared from modified /unmodified biodegradable polyesters blends with surface treated and untreated jute fibers by melt mixing and subsequent molding. Crosslinked and uncrosslinked Poly (lactic acid)/poly (caprolactone) blends were used as the biodegradable polyester matrixes. Alkali treatment was performed as the surface treatments on the jute fiber. The tensile and flexural moduli of all the fiber-reinforced composites increased with fiber content. The effect of surface treatment on the on the morphology and subsequent mechanical properties was also studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials and Methods

The poly (lactic acid) (PLA); LACEA supplied Mitsui Chemicals Japan, poly caprolactone (PCL); Celgreen PH7 supplied by Daicel and Dicumyl peroxide were used. A blend ratio of 70:30 (wt%) PLA:PCL was used. A TOYOSEIKI LABO PLASTOMILL 100CR500T-CM with internal mixer attachment Model 100C100 coupled with LABO PLASTOMILL Computer System was used for compounding at 180°C. Jute fibers were supplied by Jute Diversification Promotion Center, Dhaka, Bangladesh. Alkali treatment of jute was done with 5% NaOH solution for 2 hours at 30°C [4,5]. Evaluation of properties was done by tensile testing, thermal analysis and electron microscopy. Tensile test was carried out at 2 mm/min by means of INSTRON universal testing machine (4466, INSTRON). The cross-sectional areas of tensile fracture surfaces were observed with JEOL DATUM JSM-5200 scanning electron microscope. DSC testing was carried out under nitrogen atmosphere from ambient temperature to 200°C at a scanning rate of 10°C/min with an entry compensation DSC equipment (Pyris 1 DSC from PerkinElmer).

Figure 1: Torque & Temperature versus Time curves for PLA/PCL blending.

In Figure 1 the torque & temperature versus time curves for the preparation of PLA/PCL and the dicumyl peroxide modified blend are presented. The initial peak is the melting and fusion peak of PLA/PCL, the addition of DCP at 500s and subsequent increase in rotor speed that lead to a sudden increase in torque are followed by the stabilization of the melt. The temperature initially decreased, increased and then stabilized in response to sample addition and increase in temperature due to fusion. The subsequent stabilization of temperature indicates formation of a stable melt.

The initial investigation involved the variation of DCP content in stages from 0.1 to 2phr. From Figure 2, it can be seen that DCP concentration has tremendous influence on the mechanical properties. The most significant changes involved elongation at break (EB) that in turn dictates the toughness of the blends. The EB as a function of DCP content is therefore plotted in Figure 3. It can be seen that elongation increased tremendously and peaked off between 0.1 and 0.2 phr. Further increase in DCP concentration resulted in a decrease in EB.

Figure 2: Stress-strain curves of PLA, PCL and the 70/30 PLA/PCL blend and different DCP concentrations.

Successful improvement of toughness by adding 30 wt % of PCL and DCP to PLA improved toughness but decreased properties such as modulus and strength. At the moment the authors are exploring several options of increasing strength and stiffness that include incorporation of nano fillers, synthetic fibers as well as natural fibers.

The incorporation of natural fibers such as jute would yield totally biodegradable “green composites”. Chemical modification of jute has been shown to improve mechanical properties. A simple modification such as alkali treatment has been shown to be particularly more effective as compared to more complex chemical modifications [2]. In this study the influence of NaOH treated jute fibers were compared with that of non-treated fibers. The torque & temperature versus time curves for the compounding of the sodium hydroxide modified jute are presented in Figure 4. These are basically similar to the respective curves obtained for the DCP modified PLA/PCL blend albeit prominent peaks around 800 to 1000s indicate fiber addition.

Figure 3: Ultimate strain of PLA/PCL (70/30) blend as a function of DCP concentration.

As compared to Figure 1, it can be seen that tremendous increases in torque were recorded with increase in fiber content after which the temperature steadied. The well-defined fusion peaks indicate adequate mixing of the components.

The stress/strain curves for the various composites are shown in Figure 5. It can be seen that modulus increased with increase in fiber content albeit toughness is compromised. Figure 6 indicates that the modulus of the blends and composites increased with DCP addition and increase in fiber content respectively. It can be seen that the DCP modified PLA/PCL blend has higher modulus than the unmodified blend.

Figure 4: Torque & Temperature versus Time curves for PLA/PCL blends with different loadings of jute fiber.

Figure 5: Tensile modulus of PLA/PCL with its modified and unmodified jute composites

This could be due to hardening that resulted from crosslink network formation. The increase in modulus with increasing natural fiber content and indeed jute has been reported by several investigations. As the modulus of the fibers is much higher than that of the matrix, the rule of mixture obtains. Further more, it can be seen that the increase in modulus for the alkali treated fibers is generally higher at the respective fiber contents.

Figure 6: Tensile strength of PLA/PCL with its modified and unmodified jute composites.

This is a consequence of the chemical modification, which changes the properties of the fibers. A 9.63% loss in weight with 2 h treatment mainly involve hemicellulose removal [4] and its consequences, change in the parts of crystalline cellulose and changes in the orientation of molecular chains [5].

Figure 7: Elongation at break of PLA/PCL with its modified and unmodified jute composites.

Figure 8: normalized DSC curves of PLA/PCL blend.

From Figure 7 it can also be seen that the tensile strength of the modified fiber composites are superior to those of the unmodified ones. This indicates that the modification has been

Figure 9: Normalized DSC curves of 10-wt % jute-PLA/PCL blend composite.

effective in enhancing the strength of the composites. The EB of the composites decreased with increasing fiber composition. However it is interesting to note that the alkali treated fiber composites show superior EB in comparison to the unmodified counterparts at the respective compositions (Figure 8).

Based on the tensile properties discussed in Figures 6-8; it could be inferred that surface modification enhances the mechanical properties of thermoplastic based jute fiber composites. Several researches based on thermoset composites have reported similar observations [2].

The normalized DSC curves of PLA/PCL blend and the 10 wt % jute composite are shown in Figures 8 and 9, indicating the initial and 2nd heating curves. PLA and PCL are both polyesters in which the monomers are linked by the same ester functional group (-COOC-). It is therefore expected that this combination should yield a miscible system. Our studies involving mechanical properties as a function of composition revealed that this is indeed true. However, it is revealed here that both PCL and PLA exist mostly in separate phases due to the highly crystalline nature of both polymers. This is indicated by the respective sharp melting peaks at 60 and 165°C. The cold crystallization peak at 100 °C indicates the amorphous content of PCL. Rapid cooling from the melt and reheating more clearly highlighted the amorphous content as indicated by sharper cold crystallization peak that shifted to 110°C. Double melting peaks at 160 and 166°C are also shown. The first peak is that resulting from the melting of the less defined crystals that resulted from cold crystallization. Figure 9

Figure 10: SEM micrographs of 70/30 PCL blend and composites; (a) unmodified blend, (b) DCP modified blend, (c) alkali-treated jute fiber composite, (d) non-treated jute fiber composite.

replicates the trends in Figure 8, which is an indication that the crystalline nature of the blend is mostly kept intact even in the presence of the fibrous filler. However, the lower melting point of the crystallites attributed to cold crystallization is much smaller and occurs at a lower temperature. This indicates that the presence of the fibers has interfered with the cold crystallization process.

For network formation, the authors forecast that the free radicals resulting from DCP decomposition abstract the α -hydrogen of the ester carbonyl in each case for both PLA and PCL. The PCL radical undergoes β -scission to yield a primary radical that forms a covalent bond with the PLA radical [6,7].

The tensile fracture surfaces of PLA/PCL and the DCP modified PLA/PCL blends are shown in Figure 10. In both cases, two distinct zones were noted at the fracture surfaces. The zone of ductile failure from which fracture emanated slowly initially and then the zone of brittle fracture at which fast catastrophic failure occurred. The DCP modified blend revealed a more ductile fracture surface as indicated by the extensive crazing and fibrillation. Figure 10 also shows the surface modified and unmodified composites at 20 phr fiber loading. Both surfaces experienced brittle failure with ductile areas to a minor extent. A closer inspection revealed

that the fiber surface of the alkali treated jute is different, revealing greater details of the internal structure of the fiber as the surface wax and other minor components have been removed by the chemical treatment. This facilitates more intimate contact with the matrix material. The interface is also free from the more brittle wax hence the improvements in mechanical properties. Moreover, a rougher fiber surface upon treatment greatly contributes to extensive mechanical interlocking with the matrix.

SUMMARY

This study revealed that alkali treatment of the jute fiber improved the mechanical properties of the composite. The addition of DCP also imparted significant changes to the PLA/PCL blend as revealed by SEM. The crystalline nature of PLA and PCL are retained in the blend while the presence of jute fibers interferes with cold crystallization.

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